

THE POTENTIAL EFFECT OF GRANITE DUST ON THE GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF ABAKALIKI CLAYS

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ABSTRACT

The geotechnical properties of the Abakaliki clay soils and its response to granite treatment were investigated. The product of this treatment has been studied in this work to determine its engineering properties and potentials for use in engineering construction. Abakaliki and its environs are underlain by lateritic soils as well as marine shales, clays and sandstones of the Asu River and Ezeaku Groups. Geotechnical investigations for determination of the characteristics of clay soils in Abakaliki include chemical analysis of the clay soil and granite to determine their mutual reactions, as well as standard soil tests such as Atterberg limits, standard compaction characteristics, shear strength, and California Bearing Ratio (CBR). Results of the study show that Abakaliki clays are highly expansive soils, regarded as problem soils. The granite dust contains high amounts of the oxides of silica and alumina, and is therefore considered to have high potential for use as a soil additive. Atterberg limit tests indicate that the untreated samples of clay have high liquid limit and low plastic limit values of 47 and 19.7 respectively, while the addition of granite dust decreased and increased values from 47 - 35.1 and 19.7 to 26.3 respectively. Maximum dry density (MDD) ranges from 1.93 - 1.68mg/m³, while CBR values ranges from 4 - 44% with the addition of 0 - 20% granite dust. Shear strength tests gave an angle of shearing resistance of 23.0 - 31.89°, and cohesion values of 67.8 - 48.9kPa. Although the stabilized product degrades slightly under impact compaction, the test results suggest that it can be used for a variety of engineering purposes, but may not be sustained for a long period of time.

KEYWORDS: Geotechnical, Clay Soils, Granite, Expansive soils and Shear strength

INTRODUCTION

The challenge of geotechnical engineering practice in any part of the world is essentially the management of the soils for use in construction industry at the cheapest and safest cost. In Nigeria, for example, expansive clay soils regarded as problem soils continue to be used despite its associated problems of expansion and shrinkage which can lead to collapse of foundations. The clay minerals contained in these clays have high affinity for water which reduces consolidation and packing of soil grains. In many countries, soil additives like bottom ash, volcanic ash, cement, rice husk, and a host of others have been used to improve the strength of soils for different construction efforts. In this paper, we report the results of a project undertaken in Nigeria to evaluate the effect of granite dust on problem clays, as a means of enhancing its use as a construction material.

GEOLOGY OF THE AREA

The study area lies within the sedimentary terrain of Southeastern Nigeria, and is chiefly composed of sandstone, clay and shale lithologies. This project was done within the Abakaliki lead - zinc zone, precisely at Enyingba, Amagu and Ameri towns, Ebonyi state, Nigeria. Based on field investigations by various researchers, the study area sits within the Lower Benue Rift (Abakaliki Basin of Southern Nigeria). Reyment (1965) established the existing stratigraphic succession of the Abakaliki Basin as comprising the Asu River Group (Albian), Ezeaku Group (Turonian), and Awgu Group (Coniacian). The sedimentary successions are characterized by calcareous sandy shales and alternation of limestone in the Asu River Group, and dark grey, fissile shales with thick sandstone sequences of the Ezeaku Group. The Awgu Group, also represented here, consists of dark shales with subordinate limestones and bioturbated sandstones.

Fig. 1: Location map of the study area

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

A detailed field work to gather and analyse information on texture, sedimentary successions and composition of the various lithologic units around Abakaliki was done. Clay samples were also collected from road cuts, river channels, and outcrops for geotechnical testing. Pulverized granite (the stabilizing agent) was sourced in substantial quantity from local quarry sites in Akwanga, Nassarawa State.

Various laboratory methods are available for studying the effects of additives in stabilizing expansive soils. Common methods include geochemical analysis to identify the mineralogical composition of the soil and the intended additive, free swelling tests, Atterberg limit test, colloidal content determination, and direct measurement of volume change (Johnson and DeGraff, 1988). The following tests were performed on both the clay soils and the mixture of granite dust. They include Atterberg limits tests, Compaction tests, California bearing ratio (CBR) tests and Shear strength tests.

Expansive soils are residual products of shales and clay - shales. Altogether, ten 50kg bags of fresh clay samples and one 50kg bag of pulverized granite were collected. These samples were sent to the Soil Mechanics Laboratory at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, for analysis. The Atterberg limit, compaction and shear strength tests were carried out in accordance with the procedures specified by Lambe (1951) and the British Standards Institution (1975). Materials used for the compaction tests were those of sample sizes passing through 5mm (3/16 inch BS sieve). The CBR mould and approximately 6kg of the bulk sample were used. For the compaction test, the clay and granite samples were both oven-dried for 24 hours at 105°C, sieved and then compacted at optimum moisture content using the standard proctor compactive effort. This was done with the addition of 10, 15, and 20% granite dust to the clay sample

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical Composition of Abakaliki Clays

Clays account for nearly half the total volume of sedimentary rocks and are usually very fine grained, often less than 10⁻⁶mm in size. A number of clay minerals have been identified in the clays of Abakaliki by several researchers using X-ray diffraction techniques. They include:

- Montmorillonites, which belong to the Smectite group and often called expandable or swelling clays because they have high affinity for water.
- Illites, which are similar to muscovite but contains more silica and less potassium.

Chemical Composition of Granite

Granite dust is obtained by crushing massive boulders of granite into fine powdery form. Elemental analyses of granite dust, showing the composition of the various oxides are given in the table below.

Table 1: Chemical composition of granite (After Nockholds, 1954)

Component	Content (%)
Silica	72.08
Titanium oxide	0.37
Alumina	13.86
Ferric oxide	2.51
Magnesia (MgO)	0.52
Lime (CaO)	1.33
Potash	5.46
Manganese oxide (MnO)	0.06
Phosphoric oxide	0.18
Sodium oxide (NaO)	3.08

Atterberg Limits

The results of the liquid and plastic limit tests in the fractions passing the No.36 British Standard Sieve are summarized in the table below

Table 2: Summary of the result of Atterberg limits and linear shrinkage tests

	Control	Clay soil + 10% Granite	Clay soil + 15% Granite	Clay soil + 20% Granite
Liquid limit	47	42.0	38.5	35.1
Plastic limit	19.7	20.1	24.2	26.3
Plasticity index	18.7	10.8	11.4	13.1
Linear shrinkage (%)	12.0	4.2	3.9	3.1

Liquid limits for the various percentages of granite and clay soil are 47, 42, 38.5, and 35.1. The plastic limits are 19.7, 20.1, 24.2, and 26.3, with an average of 23; while the plasticity indices are 18.7, 10.8, 11.4, and 13.1, with an average of 15.

Araora, (2008) classified inorganic clays of soft plasticity materials as having liquid limits with the range of 25-50. Following this classification subdivision outlined in Holtz and Kovacs (1982), the clay and granite mixture would be soft.

Compaction

The compaction characteristics of the clay soil in its natural state and after treatment with varying percentages of granite dust are summarized in the table below and plotted in Fig. 2.

Table 3: Summary of compaction test results (British Standard)

Sample (%)	Maximum dry density (MDD) mg/m ²	Optimum moisture content (OMC)%
Control	1.68	17
10% Granite +clay	1.76	16
15% Granite +clay	1.77	15
20% Granite+clay	1.93	12

Fig. 2: OMC at different percentages of granite dust

Fig. 3: MDD at different percentages of granite dust

The trend shown in the table for maximum dry density (MDD) and optimum moisture content (OMC), with increasing percentages of granite dust is remarkable. The result shows that in all cases, the addition of granite at different percentages causes an increase in the MDD and a decrease in the OMC.

California Bearing Ratio (CBR)

The CBR values for unsoaked clay soils with varying mixtures of granite dust are summarized in the Table 4 and plotted in Fig.4.

Table 4: Summary of CBR test results

Compaction standard	No. of tests	Granite dust (%)	Unsoaked CBR values (%)
British Standard	2	0	4
		10	16
		15	23
		20	44

Fig. 4: CBR plots at different percentages of granite dust

From the result obtained in the table, it is clear that there is an increase in CBR value upon granite addition. The trend of increase is the same for both soaked and unsoaked conditions. Thus, the higher the dry density, the greater the CBR value at a given compactive effort. The CBR value of a construction material is often used as a benchmark in the assessment of its strength for pavement design. In practical terms, it reflects the bearing capacity of a construction material. Materials that possess high CBR values are generally regarded as satisfactory for pavement construction. On the basis of the CBR values obtained in this work, it is likely that granite treated clay samples could be used as construction material, though this would be carefully specified.

Shear Strength

The result of the unconfined compressive triaxial tests are summarized in the table below, and plots shown in Figs. 5, 6, 7, and 8.

Table 5: Summary of shear strength results

Sample No.	Cohesion (kPa)	Angle of shearing resistance (ϕ)
Control (0% granite)	67.80	23.00
10% granite + clay	61.67	26.34
15% granite + clay	54.39	28.34
20% granite + clay	48.90	31.89

Fig. 5: Mohr's envelope for stabilization with 0% granite

Fig. 6: Mohr's envelope for stabilization with 10% granite

Fig. 7: Mohr's envelope for stabilization with 15% granite

Fig. 8: Mohr's envelope for stabilization with 20% granite

The results for the triaxial tests show that cohesion decreases while angle of internal friction increased with addition of granite. The overall result nevertheless remained an increase in strength as the percentage of granite increased.

Akpokodje (1986) suggested that the progressive increase in strength with cement content in cement stabilization is as a result of both a reduction in moisture affinity of the soil grains and the formation of semi-rigid soil framework. Granite dust yields the same result and consequently acts as a border and provides the much needed hardening and strengthening properties.

Application of Granite – Stabilized Clays

Clays in their natural state contain a high proportion of fines and therefore are not regarded as good construction materials (Okogbue and Onyeobi, 1991). This is further buttressed by their swelling and shrinking ability due to clay mineral contents and their high affinity for moisture. These expandable clays that are dominant in Abakaliki area are regarded as problem soils that lack cohesion and consolidation.

Results from this work have shown that treatment of clay soils with granite dust will increase the strength characteristics of these soils and make them more suitable for engineering applications in Nigeria, such as in:

- Sub-base materials for construction of lightly to heavily trafficked roads
- Non-structural fills for construction of pavements and embankments
- Foundation materials for building

Table 6: Granite stabilized clay properties compared with Nigerian specifications

Properties of material for different layers	Nigerian specifications	Granite stabilization results	Comments
1. General filling and embankments			Very satisfactory
- Maximum dry density (MDD) (mg/m ³)	> 0.047	1.68 – 1.93	
- Optimum moisture content (OMC) (%)	< 18	12 – 17	
- Liquid limit - Plasticity index	< 40 < 20	35.1 – 47 13.1 – 18.7	
2. Sub-base course			Good
- Liquid limit	< 35	35.1 – 47	
- Plasticity index	< 16	13.1 – 18.7	
3. Base course			Poor
- Liquid limit	≤ 30	35.1 – 47	
- Plasticity index	≤ 13	13.1 – 18.7	

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions are drawn from this research:

- Granite dust is cheap and readily available and therefore can be used in substantial quantity to stabilize soils
- Based on AASHTO classifications, the Abakaliki clay soil which has a plasticity index of 18.7 and a liquid limit of 47 can be rated as soft soils and therefore requires improvement to make it suitable for construction.
- The stabilized product can be used in Nigeria for a number of engineering purposes namely sub-base course, general filling of embankments, as well as in pavement construction

- When compacted at the standard proctor effort, the clay and granite mixture has a reasonable strength. The strength is expected to increase at higher densities. This property would make the material suitable for use in non-structural site fills, light weight structural fills and as a cover material for sanitary land fills
- Abakaliki clays contain clay minerals such as montmorillonite, which is known as swelling clays, because of its high affinity for moisture; and illite. When engineering works are constructed on such soils, serious structural damage which requires huge sums of money to rectify may result.

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